

QUALITY MANAGEMENT THEORY AND ITS APPLICATION IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION

Narimonova Saida Narimon's kizi

Independent researcher of Institute of retraining and professional development of
directors and specialists of pre-school educational organizations

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Abstract: In this article, the important methodological importance of educational quality management mechanisms in preschool educational organizations, the principles of educational quality management, and the specific features of the preschool educational system are presented.

Key words: quality management, quality assurance , principle of objectivity, principle of interaction, quality management of education, systematic approach

Quality management as one of the types of general management appeared at the beginning of the 20th century. Its appearance is closely related to the rapid economic development of a number of countries, which has sharply raised the issues of product quality assurance.

Since 1960, the concept of traditional control has been replaced by the concept of total quality management (control) (Total Quality Control). This marked the transition to the third stage of development of the theory and practice of quality management . According to Feigenbaum, the production of a product is nothing but the creation of quality, so the process of creating a product is a controlled process. Therefore, as the concept of control-based quality assurance implies, it is important not only to identify defects, but also to determine the causes of their occurrence and develop measures to regulate the production process to stabilize the quality level. Thus, in Feigenbaum's concept, control is considered not as the main and only operation, but as a link of an integrated system of quality assurance.

The result of the above three stages in the development of the theory and practice of quality management was the confirmation of the priority of quality in world production. At the end of the 1980s, the idea of total quality management (TQM - Total Quality Management), its essence is quality assurance at all stages of product production and the responsibility of all employees of the enterprise for this process. This was the beginning of the fourth stage of the development of a scientifically based quality management system .

International standards of the ISO 9000-1:1994, 8402:1994, 9004-2 family define the leading terms that make up the conceptual apparatus of quality management. These include: quality, supplier, customer, needs, service, process, quality program, quality assurance, quality management.

According to the ISO definition, quality is the set of characteristics that give a product or service its ability to meet specified or intended needs . In this definition, new emphasis is clearly visible in understanding the essence of quality. The latter will begin to be considered from the point of view of compliance with consumer requirements. The standard provides clarification of stated and implied needs. The former is clearly defined in a contractual or regulated environment. In other circumstances, needs are identified.

A supplier is an organization that supplies a product or provides a service. At the same time, the standards allow replacing the term "supplier" with the term "organization".

A consumer means a recipient of a product or service provided by a supplier (organization) .

Service is the result of direct interaction between the supplier, the consumer and the supplier's internal activities to satisfy the consumer 's needs .

A quality program is a document that specifies specific measures in the field of quality related to the allocation of resources and the determination of the sequence of actions to obtain a certain product.

Quality assurance is a system of planned and regularly implemented activities that help produce products that meet quality requirements.

Focusing on innovation management as a functional system of management, many authors describe it as "an independent field of economic science and professional activity aimed at forming and ensuring the achievement of innovation goals of any organizational structure through the rational use of material, labor and financial resources." In this respect, innovative management is a direct object of innovative processes in all sectors of the national economy and represents one of the many types of emerging functional management.

Innovative management in the management of the preschool education system is the main and mandatory condition for ensuring healthy competitiveness, gaining one's position in society, and increasing efficiency.

The methodological basis of preschool education quality management is the principles of objectivity, interaction and development. Below we consider the principles of development.

The principle of objectivity . This general scientific principle is related to the dialectical-materialist interpretation of the cognitive process. Its core is the recognition of the objectivity of scientific knowledge, which accurately or approximately accurately reflects the objective existing reality. But at the same time, the objective properties, connections and relationships of the external world reflected in the mind of the perceiving subject become the subject of his knowledge, from which he draws certain conclusions, one or another relationship is formed.

These subjective moments correspond to the objective content if the pedagogues and leaders of the preschool educational organization that implements quality management of the educational process have good theoretical training.

Since the quality management process of preschool education always includes a sufficient number of subjective factors related to, first of all, the selection of assessment indicators, the use of appropriate assessment procedures, the correct interpretation of the data obtained during the expert assessment process, etc., achieving the objectivity and accuracy of the obtained data. and it is important to seek to evaluate it.

Implementation of this principle includes:

- to distinguish the important features that determine the quality of the educational process from the unimportant features that occur under the influence of temporary factors, and as a result - to choose the right direction of management influence;
- study of the educational process in unity of its quantitative and qualitative characteristics;
- review the quality of the educational process and its results in the context of specific circumstances of the external and internal plan;
- use of control and assessment tools that meet the requirements of information content, objectivity and reliability[3].

The principle of interaction . Any pedagogical event, regardless of the conditions of its implementation , does not exist by itself, separately, but only based on the interaction of the

surrounding reality with other processes. Interaction is a way of connecting the elements of any structure, a necessary condition for its variability and stability, therefore, getting into the essence of the object involves considering it through various relationships with other phenomena of pedagogical activity. Knowing the mechanism of interaction of certain objects, it is possible to imagine their state at any time.

It's a problem we're studying The principle of interaction includes :

- the state of the educational process, its results and these factors (external and internal) that caused them and forecasting their future changes on this basis; use the results of analysis and forecasting as a basis for designing the quality of preschool education;
- consider the quality of preschool education as a set of characteristics (integral and simple), reveal the mechanism of their interaction;
- study of quality management in the relationship between its procedural and effective components;
- establishing necessary connections between structural and functional components of educational quality management ;
- a healthy mental environment among employees in the post-school educational organization during the implementation of educational process activities .

As for the problem of managing the quality of education in a preschool educational institution, a systematic approach implies the following:

1. Studying the organization of preschool education as a complex system: determining its structure; establishing internal relations forming its structure, features of interaction with the external environment; to determine its specific characteristics and to evaluate it correctly .
2. Knowing the object of management related to determining the potential of the preschool educational organization as an educational organization that ensures quality , its formation and development .
3. Considering quality management as an open system interacting with the external environment; it is characterized by the existence of a set of interrelated actions necessary to achieve the quality of education and fulfill the tasks of forming the management process .

A systematic genetic approach reveals the mechanisms of succession in the development of systems. The following rules of the systematic genetic approach are of particular importance in studying the problem of managing the quality of preschool education:

1. Two of organization and management (stability and variability). is reflected in the bilateral law. This rule justifies the need to organize operational management in the conditions of interaction of the preschool educational organization with the external environment and development management related to the use of innovative activities aimed at changing the structure and characteristics of the preschool educational organization . It is the taste of determining its essence and transitioning to a new state of quality .
2. activation as a basis for developing and maintaining any system to determine the principle of The application of this rule in solving the problems of quality management of preschool education implies the following: a) determining the conformity of the organizational structure of the management with the organization of preschool education ; b) adapting the functional structure of management to the goals of providing quality education. preschool educational organizations are the leading rules of the integrated approach, which are indicated in connection with the specific features of the preschool education system :

1. To justify the need to organize management in their appropriate combination to meet the needs of the preschool educational organization , as well as the interests and needs of the participants of its educational process.
2. Determining the contradiction between stability and variability as a source of self-management development , on the one hand, -is expressed in maintaining the main features of the preschool educational organization that ensure optimal results, and on the other hand, in its self-management. Directing development through effective use of external and internal resources.

In the development of the theory of educational quality management in pre-school educational organizations , a number of factors formed by psychology and pedagogy rules and principles are of fundamental methodological importance.

The ideas and rules of management theory can serve as a methodological basis for the development of the theoretical foundations of educational quality management in a preschool educational organization :

- pedagogical management concept ;
- software-targeted management and its clarification in relation to management ;
- concept of managing the development of educational systems ;
- the idea of the complexity of the subject of quality management, which emphasizes the need to clearly divide the obligations of employees, the functions they perform, and strengthen the principles of coordination in the implementation of professional activities;
- approaches to management efficiency assessment.

The above approaches and rules form the methodological basis for studying the theoretical foundations of educational quality management in a preschool educational organization. In conclusion, the main reason for the identified contradictions, which are a serious obstacle to the movement of preschool education practice on the path of quality education, is insufficient quality management of education in preschool education organizations. This is directly related to the fact that the theoretical, methodological and technological foundations of such management have not been developed.

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